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DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COGNITIVE INTERESTS

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Abstract: *This article presents ideas about the development of knowledge-based interests of students, the stages of manifestation of creative interests, intellectual and emotional activity of students, and independent reading activities of students. Also, what to teach elementary school students and what tools, books and reading development, components of reading activity were analyzed.*

Key words: *Pupils, interest, creative interest, learning, personal activity, primary education.*

Introduction. Knowledge-based interest creates the need to form causal links. As a result, students begin to determine the specifics of this connection. At this stage, students are faced with certain problems. Students, on the other hand, seek to find solutions to these problems in a conscious way. Knowledge-based interests distance students from ignorance. The realization of new aspects of objective being ensures that they rise to new stages of intellectual development. As a result, the active character of students is ensured: self-control, faith in willpower, initiative and optimism in the process of work, the manifestation of a desire for self-improvement and development.

The stage of manifestation of creative interests includes: independence, the reshaped activity of the student, the application of methods that provide new solutions to the problems facing them, the manifestation of their creative abilities, etc.

Interest in reading is an interest that expresses the students' desire to explore and apply the ancestral experience expressed in books. To do this, mental and emotional activity should be formed in students. Mental as well as emotional activity are manifested in books as the main goal-oriented component, serving to provide students with social experience. Because in the books this experience is preserved and presented from ancestors to descendants. Accordingly, knowledge-based interests are choice-based interests and primarily promote the development of the intellectual sphere of students. With the help of interest, students actively engage in the assimilation of knowledge in a particular area. A book will help them closely in this.

The importance of knowledge-related interests for the development of personality is that in IT, activities in a particular area activate the educational processes of the student under the influence of interest. Gives students intellectual satisfaction and emotional uplifting. Cognitive interests are motivations for individual activity and promote the development of cognitive activity.

Main tasks. One of the main tasks of primary education is the formation of interest in fiction in readers through the means of reading. It is one of the important issues, and books and Reading are of great importance in educating and developing students.

In his time, the famous educator V.A.Sukhomlinsky had likened the books to a window where readers would explore the outside world.

Reading is a pedagogical phenomenon that determines what to teach elementary students and by what means to develop their interest in fiction. With the help of reading, Not only speech and mental activity is formed, but a certain set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies of a general nature are formed.

In the educational and extracurricular pedagogical processes of all educational subjects, students are formed the skills to engage in communication with the book. Reading activity refers to the desire to enter the labor of reading. The perception of reality in the book contributes to a deeper understanding of its content. When the book is fully read, the reader should be able to think about it.

Independent reading activities of Primary School students are of an individual nature. In the process, without the support of the teacher, students enter the communication environment expressed in the book. As a result, readers will have the opportunity to consciously choose the work they are reading and, alternatively, to master it by reading it independently during their acquaintance with the book.

Reading activities have three main components of their own:

- students ' awareness of the motives and goals of conscious reference to the book;
- have knowledge of the world of books;
- their understanding of the content of the read book based on their capabilities.

At this stage, students should not be allowed to be pressured by the teacher. It is important that readers read books not out of obligation, but out of desire. One of the peculiarities of children's books lies in the abundance of pictures and illustrations in them. Such illustrations create a strong interest in the book in them, emotionally affecting young school-age students.

Creating conditions for students to communicate as much as possible with their teachers and parents about the books they read also serves to increase interest in them. It helps to generate more conversations, mutual exchange of ideas, discussions and situations of knowing and discussing what they do not know, among adults with students.

From the elementary grades, each student should have his own favorite books. These books primarily affect the area of their interests and promote their effective development. To do this, teachers, parents should show their positive attitude towards the book and become an example for children. For this purpose, it is required to organize reading minutes with them every day. It is advisable to regularly introduce readers to books on the internet pages or various social rollers with a reflection of reading. Generating a positive attitude towards books ensures that students easily assimilate educational materials, approach texts in textbooks, pictures with a special interest. The more texts and images in textbooks are selected in a way that suits educational goals and age characteristics of students, the more intensively their knowledge-based interests develop.

Observations suggest that readers ' interest in books containing examples of fiction has been somewhat fading in recent years. This condition can be observed among students of different ages.

Parents and teachers often note that students do not want to read books in a large hajm, are limited to viewing short texts and serials taken about a particular work, and books with pictures and

illustrations do not interest them at all. As a result of this, students do not develop the skills of working with a book, perceiving the content of works of art. Educators, sociologists, psychologists, and philosophers have repeatedly argued that this negatively affects the progress of individual spirituality. It is advisable for students to systematically organize reading sessions, starting with elementary grades, with students realizing that they love works of art, are more eager to read them, have an effective impact on the formation of their interests. Only then will it be easy for students to master learning materials. Teachers should be able to determine what books are of interest to their readers, what genres they read samples of folk oral creativity and children's literature with special interest. To do this, it is advisable for the teacher to conduct conversations, questions and answers with each student in the direction of books and reading.

It should be noted that it is at school that the enthusiasm for reading in students decreases or gradually disappears. This is evidenced by the fact that teachers control the development of the student's skills regarding reading techniques in each class. Such control is annoying for readers and makes them tired of books. Students read a specific book according to the teacher's assignment, but for them this work will not be interesting at all. Reading becomes an interesting activity for them only when readers selectively read samples of fiction based on their desires.

We will try to show below the reasons that led to a decrease in interest in reading in readers:

- the strong influence of the media on readers, the development of Science and technology, including the emergence of various gadgets and the impact they exert;
- the fact that in most families there is absolutely no focus on children reading books;
- the fact that after the students went to school, the decline in the activities of parents about reading to them was decided by the opinion that there was no need for this;
- the absence of mechanisms for the formation of a systematic reading activity for readers.

Teachers in most cases do not express an incentive to teach their students to communicate with the book. Because, teaching younger students to communicate with a book is a complex pedagogical phenomenon. And without teaching reading, it is impossible to form an interest in the samples of fiction in them.

Conclusion. Thus, an increase in vocabulary as a result of teaching its readers to communicate with the book in a planned manner will allow them to achieve the expected efficiency. For younger students, activities such as making words by harmonizing different harps, interpreting the meaning of words, will be interesting. Such training makes it possible to gradually attract them to the library. As a result of the regular practice of teachers and parents, the academic performance of students increases.

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